

Site: SPHINX
TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16A Locus Number 3b

Progress of Excavation 23/1/80 R16A1: (3) cleared down to (3b)

Surface slopes down radically to W. Bone showing embedded in
 dry fine sandy patch of 3b just where (4) showing terminates

Also: granite frag showing upper NE corner R16A1. Maybe only
 surface drying out, but (3b) patchy w/ compact moist tan clay-like

interspersed w/ fairly packed dry fine buff sand. Is this remains

of (harder packed (3)?) Excavation begins at E side high point,

scrapping w/ trowel and tip action dislodging matrix. At S side,

on edge former N Balk, pod-like impressions in clay. There may be →

Locus Description COMPACT FINE TAN CLAY-LIKE SAND

Location in Square _____

Under Locus (3) CLEAN SAND Over Locus (4) - (4d)

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____

Insect larvae burrows as some insect hulls recovered. 24/1/80: Working down matrix looks subtly mottled w/ faint traces clean quartz like sand interspersed as pockets in more compact clay-like charcoal flecks interspersed throughout. 10-20 cm down larger frags limestone, 2 large frags granite.

NOTE: HOLES (called "pod-like impressions" very likely insect as live worm found in one.)

③b Directly over ④ (and going under rectangular block on which toppled cb rests cleared first. Became apparent that what was thought also ③b banked against cut through 4-4d on W^{is} another deposit. Comes up much looser, lighter, sandier than ③b This designated ③c and cleared ~~separately~~.

Plan of surface 3b so amended and R16 N BALK

31/1/80 R16A2: Cleared 3b down to average level of top of 4 in R16, R16A1. Here kind of an arbitrary level as ③b - compact TAN CLAY, phases into ④ with no clear demarcation. But took ③b down to level (8.36) of top of ④ and seems deposit may get slightly more gravelly here. This general level (top of ④) fairly flush w/ ledge (bedrock) protruding from under c.b. of N S.T. wall. Some fine gravelly lenses in ③b - (see R16A1, N BALK), scattered carbon spots (small). 1 large black fracture CRW thick sherd. 1 wall of burnished red ware bowl, thin (Large sherd).

STONE MATERIAL SIFTED OUT CONSISTS OF FINE ^{SOME GRANITE} LIMESTONE CHIPS, SEVERAL LARGE LIMESTONE FRAGS, 2-3 LARGE GRANITE FRAGS, 1 LARGE ALABASTER FRAG.